

Amyand's Appendicitis in Giant Inguinoscrotal Hernia with 18 Years of Evolution: Case Report and Literature Review

Joana Monique Castillo Escobar*¹, Victoria Alejandra Sarmiento Alvarado², Pablo Daniel Heráldez León³, Francisco Aurelio Sanchez Osorio⁴, Gabriela Citlalli Gutiérrez Viveros⁵, Estefany Alejo Rocha⁶, Lilia Mercedes Lavariega Del Pino⁷, Tomás Alberto Ríos Chico⁸, Ana Paola Quebrado Apolineo⁶, Antonio Pastor Hernandez⁹, Jorge Daniel Velázquez López⁶, Ángela Patricia López Alvarado¹⁰

¹Hospital Regional ISSSTE Veracruz.

²Universidad Nacional Autónoma de Honduras, Hospital Escuela.

³Universidad Michoacana de San Nicolás de Hidalgo. Facultad de Ciencias Médicas y Biológicas "Dr. Ignacio Chávez".

⁴Instituto de Pós Graduação Médica Carlos Chagas.

⁵Instituto Politécnico Nacional, Escuela Nacional de Medicina y Homeopatía.

⁶Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México.

⁷Instituto de estudios superiores de Chiapas, Campus Tapachula.

⁸Universidad Autónoma de Chihuahua.

⁹Instituto Politécnico Nacional, Escuela Superior de Medicina.

¹⁰Universidad Autónoma de Coahuila.

ABSTRACT

Giant inguinoscrotal hernia is a rare entity, generally resulting from prolonged evolution without adequate treatment. Its surgical correction poses significant challenges due to loss of abdominal domain and the risk of abdominal compartment syndrome after reduction of the hernia contents. Amyand's appendicitis, defined as the presence of an inflamed cecal appendix within the hernia sac, represents a rare condition whose coincidence with a giant hernia is exceptional. We present the case of a 41-year-old male patient with an 18-year history of a right inguinoscrotal hernia who was admitted with acute abdominal pain. During surgery, a hernia sac measuring 40 × 30 cm containing ileal loops, free fluid, and an inflamed appendix was identified. Appendectomy, segmental ileal resection with side-to-side anastomosis were performed, and the abdomen was left open using negative pressure therapy due to the high risk of abdominal compartment syndrome. The postoperative course was favorable. This case represents a rare combination reported in the literature and highlights the need for an individualized surgical approach, avoiding prosthetic materials in contaminated contexts and considering strategies such as open abdomen in giant hernias with loss of domain.

KEYWORDS: Giant inguinal hernia, Amyand's appendicitis, complicated hernia, vermiform appendix, open abdomen.

ARTICLE DETAILS

Published On:
11 August 2025

Available on:
<https://ijmscrs.com>

INTRODUCTION

Inguinal hernia is one of the most common surgical pathologies worldwide, accounting for up to 75% of all abdominal hernias. It typically presents as a reducible protrusion in the inguinal region and is usually treated electively. However, in some cases, the hernia may evolve for years without medical attention, leading to what is known as a giant inguinal hernia—an advanced and uncommon form of

the disease. This is defined as a hernia that extends beyond half the length of the thigh when standing or contains a large portion of intra-abdominal contents, resulting in loss of abdominal domain. Its repair poses major challenges due to difficulty of reduction, risk of intra-abdominal hypertension, and the need for complex reconstructive techniques.

On the other hand, Amyand's appendicitis is a rare entity, first described in 1735 by Claudius Amyand, who performed the

Amyand's Appendicitis in Giant Inguinoscrotal Hernia with 18 Years of Evolution: Case Report and Literature Review

first appendectomy on a patient with appendicitis within an inguinal hernia. This condition specifically refers to the presence of the cecal appendix within the inguinal hernia sac, whether normal, inflamed, perforated, or showing signs of acute appendicitis. Its incidence is low, estimated between 0.07% and 1% of all inguinal hernias, and diagnosis is usually made intraoperatively because clinical and imaging findings are nonspecific.

The combination of a giant inguinal hernia with long evolution and acute intra-hernial appendicitis (Amyand) is extremely unusual, with few cases reported in the literature. Preoperative diagnosis is uncommon due to the chronicity of the hernia masking typical signs of appendicitis. This situation presents important considerations for the surgical approach since it involves not only repair of a complex hernia but also resection of the inflamed organ, with implications for prosthetic use, infection risk, and surgical planning.

This article aims to describe the case of a patient with an 18-year-old giant inguinoscrotal hernia in which acute Amyand's appendicitis was found during surgical exploration. The clinical course, intraoperative findings, surgical management, and a review of related medical literature are presented. This report seeks to contribute to the limited existing evidence on comprehensive management of such unique cases requiring careful surgical planning and clinical judgment.

CLINICAL CASE

A 41-year-old male patient with no relevant medical history presented to the emergency department with progressive enlargement of the right inguinoscrotal region, accompanied by recent onset abdominal pain, nausea, and a feeling of distension. The patient reported having had the hernia since age 23 (18 years of evolution), with gradual increase in size and no prior treatment due to economic barriers and fear of surgery (Figure 1,2,3).

Figures 1,2: images prior to the surgical event.

Figure 3: images prior to the surgical event.

Amyand's Appendicitis in Giant Inguinoscrotal Hernia with 18 Years of Evolution: Case Report and Literature Review

Physical examination revealed a giant, irreducible right inguinoscrotal hernia measuring approximately 40 × 30 cm, extending below the middle third of the thigh when standing. The overlying skin was thin but without signs of ischemia. Bowel sounds were audible in the hernia sac, suggesting intestinal contents.

Contrast-enhanced abdominal and pelvic CT scan showed a large herniation of small bowel loops and free fluid within the sac, without signs of pneumoperitoneum or complete

intestinal obstruction. Emergency surgery was decided under the diagnosis of complicated inguinoscrotal hernia.

Exploratory laparotomy and dissection of the hernia sac revealed ileal loops, abundant serous fluid, and an inflamed cecal appendix, prompting appendectomy. Ischemic ileal segments due to chronic strangulation were identified, and segmental ileal resection (~40 cm) with mechanical side-to-side anastomosis was performed (**Figure 4,5,6**).

Figure 4: hernia sac.

Due to loss of abdominal domain from chronic hernia and the high risk of abdominal compartment syndrome after content reduction, primary abdominal wall closure was deferred. An

open abdomen strategy with staged delayed closure was implemented.

Figures 5,6: appendicitis and ileum lesion.

The patient was transferred to intensive care, started on enteral feeding on postoperative day five, and underwent regular open abdomen reviews (Figure 7). Clinical evolution was favorable, with good diet tolerance, adequate intestinal adaptation, and no local or systemic infectious complications during initial hospitalization.

Figure 7: open abdomen

DISCUSSION

Giant inguinoscrotal hernia is uncommon in countries with timely surgical access but still occurs in regions with socioeconomic barriers, as in this case. It is defined as a hernia exceeding the middle third of the thigh when standing or associated with significant loss of abdominal domain—the inability of the abdominal cavity to accommodate its organs due to their chronic migration into the hernia sac. This condition carries significant surgical and pathophysiological risks, including abdominal compartment syndrome after abrupt reduction, with risk of multiorgan dysfunction.

The presence of the appendix within an inguinal hernia, known as Amyand's appendicitis, is a rare surgical occurrence with incidence below 1%. The acute appendicitis variant is even rarer, posing a diagnostic challenge since clinical signs are often masked by the complicated hernia. In most cases, diagnosis is incidental during surgery, as with our patient.

The Losanoff and Basson classification guides management. Our patient corresponded to type 3, characterized by complicated appendicitis within a hernia with intestinal involvement, requiring appendectomy, bowel resection, and avoidance of mesh due to infection risk.

In this case, ileal resection and side-to-side anastomosis were performed due to intestinal ischemia associated with chronicity and probable sustained torsion. The decision to maintain an open abdomen with negative pressure therapy was critical to prevent abdominal compartment syndrome—a strategy supported in literature for giant hernias with loss of domain. This approach allows gradual reduction of abdominal contents, improves visceral perfusion, and facilitates delayed fascial closure with lower respiratory, hemodynamic, and digestive complications.

The scarcity of similar published cases highlights the rarity and academic value of this presentation. Previous reports note that hernias untreated over 10 years carry higher risks of intestinal ischemia, perforation, and infections. However, few document coexistence of giant inguinal hernia with Amyand's appendicitis and bowel resection, making this a valuable contribution to surgical literature.

This case illustrates the importance of a multidisciplinary approach with preoperative planning, hemodynamic evaluation, and individualized abdominal closure strategies. Intraoperative diagnosis of Amyand's appendicitis should alert surgeons to adapt technique and limit permanent prosthetic use when infection risk exists.

CONCLUSION

Giant inguinoscrotal hernia is a rare but clinically challenging entity, especially in cases of prolonged evolution without treatment. Its management requires careful surgical planning considering the risks of loss of abdominal domain and potential complications related to its contents.

The presence of Amyand's appendicitis in the context of a giant hernia adds complexity to management, requiring intraoperative decisions such as appendectomy, intestinal resection, and safest abdominal closure technique. In this case, open abdomen strategy prevented compartment syndrome and facilitated progressive patient recovery.

This report underscores the importance of intraoperative diagnosis, individualized surgical treatment, and close postoperative monitoring in patients with long-standing hernias. It also contributes to the limited literature on coexistence of Amyand's appendicitis and ischemic bowel within a giant inguinoscrotal hernia, providing useful evidence for future similar cases.

REFERENCES

- I. Shaban, Y., et al. (2018). Amyand's hernia: A case report and review of the literature. *International Journal of Surgery Case Reports*, 52, 145–149. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijscr.2018.01.021>
- II. Khalid, H., et al. (2021). Amyand's hernia: A case report. *Annals of Medicine and Surgery*, 68, 102–107. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.amsu.2021.04.017>
- III. Choi, C. C. M., et al. (2024). Amyand's hernia with concurrent appendicitis: A case report. *International Journal of Surgery Case Reports*. Advance online publication. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijscr.2024.01.001>
- IV. Riojas-Garza, A., et al. (2023). Case report: Amyand's hernia in a patient with acute perforated appendicitis. *Surgical Case Reports*. Advance online publication. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40792-023-01597-9>
- V. Corvatta, F. A., et al. (2023). Incarcerated left-sided Amyand's hernia and synchronous ipsilateral femoral hernia: First case report. *Surgical Case Reports*, 9, 15. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40792-023-01597-9>
- VI. Nakamura, Y., et al. (2023). Amyand hernia repair and negative pressure wound therapy. *Annals of Case Reports*, 8, 1532. <https://doi.org/10.21767/2471-8041.1001532>
- VII. Cankorkmaz, L., Ozer, H., Guney, C., Atalar, M. H., & Arslan, M. S. (2010). Amyand's hernia in children: A single center experience. *Surgery*, 147(1), 1–3. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.surg.2009.09.021>
- VIII. Nikolovski, A., et al. (2024). Giant inguinal hernia left untreated for 40 years: Case report. *Journal of Surgical Case Reports*, 2024(11), rjae734. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jscr/rjae734>
- IX. Basukala, S., et al. (2021). Bilateral giant inguinoscrotal hernia: A case report. *International Journal of Surgery Case Reports*, 82, 105–108. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijscr.2021.05.025>

- X. Trakarnsagna, A., et al. (2014). Giant inguinal hernia: Report of a case and reviews of surgical techniques. *International Journal of Surgery Case Reports*, 5(6), 365–369.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijscr.2014.05.005>
- XI. Sanjay, R., et al. (2021). Case report of a giant inguinal hernia causing intestinal obstruction. *International Surgery Journal*, 8(8), 2463–2468.
<https://doi.org/10.18203/2349-2902.isj20213038>
- XII. Ishii, K., et al. (2017). Duodenal rupture due to giant inguinal hernia: A case report. *International Journal of Surgery Case Reports*. Advance online publication.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijscr.2017.07.032>
- XIII. Bansod, P. Y., et al. (2017). Scrotal abdomen: Case of giant inguinal hernia. *JSM General Surgery Cases and Images*, 2(1), 1022.
<https://doi.org/10.24966/GSCS-0076/100022>
- XIV. Cheatham, M. L., Malbrain, M. L. N. G., Kirkpatrick, A. W., et al. (2013). Intra-abdominal hypertension and abdominal compartment syndrome: Updated consensus definitions and clinical practice guidelines. *Intensive Care Medicine*, 39(7), 1190–1202.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s00134-013-2907-z>
- XV. Hutchinson, R. (1993). Amyand's hernia. *Journal of the Royal Society of Medicine*, 86(2), 104–105.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/014107689308600208>